

HYDROXYKETONES. PART VIII. THE FRIES REACTION OF THE ESTERS OF ANISIC ACID AND A STUDY OF ITS MECHANISM

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Fries migrations of the esters of anisic acid with phenol and isomeric cresols have been studied. It has been observed that the methoxyl group does not interfere in the reaction and normal migration products are obtained.

During the course of our earlier studies on the mechanism of the Fries reaction (Saharia and Sharma, this *Journal*, 1956, 33, 788; *J. Sci. Ind. Res.*, 1957, 16B, 125), it was observed that steric factors played an important part and unless the phenoxy oxygen atom was available to form the complex (I), no migration took place, although the carbonyl group might be sterically free to form the complex. This observation rules out the idea of some workers (Ralston *et al.*, *J. Org. Chem.*, 1940, 5, 645, 2165; 1941, 6, 751; Amin and Shah, *J. Univ. Bombay*, 1948, 17, 1) that the carbonyl oxygen atom is important for the complex formation in this reaction.

Another important factor in the Fries migration, worth considering, is the electron density at the phenoxy oxygen atom. This aspect of the problem arises only when there is another electron donor group competing for the complex formation. The present communication presents a study of the Fries reaction involving the esters of anisic acid. During the earlier work with *m*-methoxybenzoic acid esters (Saharia and Sharma, *loc. cit.*), it was observed that the methoxyl group was preferred for the complex formation though it occurred also at the phenoxy oxygen atom, while with the esters of *o*-methoxybenzoic acid, steric factors played a major role. Based on the results obtained during the migrations of the esters of anisic acid, it is evident that the electron density at the methoxyl group is insufficient for complex formation, which takes place at the phenoxy oxygen atom, as normal migration products are obtained.

The study of the Fries migration of the esters of the three isomeric methoxybenzoic acids therefore leads us to the conclusion that the electron density at the phenoxy oxygen atom and its availability against any steric factors for the complex formation are the necessary requirements for the reaction to proceed; the carbonyl group does not play any important part in this migration. During the

present work the Fries reactions were studied at 120° and 160°, and it was observed that temperature had little effect on the course of the reaction though comparable yields of the hydroxyketones were obtained in some cases at the two temperatures.

An important observation made during the course of this study was the non-formation of the *o*-hydroxyketones even at 160°; phenyl anisate, when migrated at 160°, afforded negligibly small traces of the *ortho*-ketone, which could not be isolated in spite of repeated efforts. However, *m*- and *p*-cresyl anisates gave exclusively the *o*-hydroxyketones at 120° and 160°.

Phenyl anisate alone gave the demethylated ketone at 160°, while in no other case demethylation was observed.

The hydroxyketones were characterised through their 2:4-dinitrophenylhydrazones.

EXPERIMENTAL

Anisic acid, required for this work, was prepared in good yields from *p*-hydroxybenzoic acid by the method of Kalf and Robinson (*J. Chem. Soc.*, 1925, 1970) and was then converted into anisoyl chloride by refluxing with thionyl chloride. The esters of phenol and isomeric cresols were prepared by the Schotten-Baumann reaction.

The Fries migration of these esters was carried out using 1.3 moles of anhydrous aluminium chloride for one mole of the ester in absence of any solvent at 120° and 160°, and the reaction products worked up in the customary manner. It was observed that at the lower temperature, the yields of the hydroxyketones were slightly better and that some free anisic acid was recovered in most of the cases.

TABLE I

Esters.	
I. Phenyl anisate :	Colorless needles from dilute ethanol, m.p. 75-76° (lit. 76°).
II. <i>o</i> -Cresyl anisate :	Colorless needles from dilute ethanol m.p. 65°. (Found : C, 73.9; H, 5.3; C ₁₅ H ₁₄ O ₃ requires C, 74.4; H, 5.8%).
III. <i>m</i> -Cresyl anisate :	Colorless plates from dilute ethanol m.p. 60°. (Found: C, 71.6; H, 6.1; C ₁₅ H ₁₄ O ₃ , 1/2H ₂ O requires C, 71.7; H, 6.0%).
IV. <i>p</i> -Cresyl anisate :	Colorless plates from dilute ethanol, m.p. 67°. (Found: C, 74.5; H; 5.8, C ₁₅ H ₁₄ O ₃ requires C, 74.4; H, 5.8%).

Hydroxyketones

1. Phenyl anisate (I) gave two ketones (*a* & *b*) at 160°, which were separated by their solubility difference in benzene, and only one (*a*) at 120°.

(*a*). 4-Hydroxy-4'-methoxybenzophenone was crystallised from benzene in needles, m.p. 150-51° (lit. 151°).

(*b*). 4:4'-Dihydroxybenzophenone was obtained in small yields and crystallised from ethanol in needles, m.p. 206-207° (lit. 205-207°).

2. The ester (II) gave *3-methyl-4-hydroxy-4'-methoxybenzophenone*, which was crystallised from dilute ethanol in orange needles, m.p. 186°. (Found: C, 73.8; H, 5.3. $C_{15}H_{14}O_3$ requires C, 74.4; H, 5.8%). Its 2:4-dinitrophenylhydrazone had m. p. 221-2°.

3. The ester (III) gave *2-hydroxy-4-methyl-4'-methoxybenzophenone*, which on crystallisation from ethanol in lustrous needles had m.p. 96-97°. (Found: C, 74.6; H, 6.5. $C_{15}H_{14}O_3$ requires C, 74.4; H, 5.8%).

It gave a violet coloration with ferric chloride and its 2:4-dinitrophenylhydrazone had m.p. 198-200°.

4. The ester (IV) furnished *2-hydroxy-5-methyl-4'-methoxybenzophenone*; it was crystallised from petroleum ether in colorless plates, m.p. 108-109° (lit. m.p. 108-109°).

It gave a violet coloration with ferric chloride and its 2:4-dinitrophenylhydrazone had m.p. 208-209°.

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